

UDC [305: 005.3]-029:1T. V. ANDRUSHCHENKO^{1*}, O. V. CHEREDNYK^{2*}, R. O. BELOZOROVA^{3*}^{1*}National Pedagogical Dragomanov University (Kyiv, Ukraine), e-mail tanya_atv@ukr.net, ORCID 0000-0001-6701-8035^{2*}Donbas State Pedagogical University (Sloviansk, Ukraine), e-mail 21raduga-duga21@ukr.net, ORCID 0000-0002-6547-267X^{3*}National Pedagogical Dragomanov University (Kyiv, Ukraine), e-mail renabel@ukr.net, ORCID 0000-0002-5032-6653**GENDER ASPECTS OF RELATIONSHIP IN THE SYSTEM OF MANAGEMENT**

Purpose. The purpose of this paper is the study of gender aspects of management and relationship between management characteristic and style of leadership from gender typing in order to improve management efficiency. **Theoretical basis.** To understand the influence of gender mechanisms on the organization's governance system, it turns out that there is a difference in the approach of women and men to management and leadership. The main characteristics of male and female leadership style, features in making management decisions regarding work and career are given. **Originality** of a paper is the further development in the theory of gender processes with application of interdisciplinary approaches in studying the phenomenon of gender, not from the point of view of the interactions between two large social groups (men and women), but as a social resource of an organization where men and women represent labor potential, rational use of which is the key to successful management in the organization. The social potential of Ukrainian women can become a valuable resource in a country, a region, and any social organization. **Conclusions.** In modern society, the unique experience of women's rule is ignored, indicating that they have significant and little used management potential. An analysis of gender interactions in management processes revealed the active desire of women for career growth and success in individual image. However, the transformation of the gender sphere in an organization reflects the preference of patriarchal relations, which is an obstacle to the advancement of women in the managerial structure and, accordingly, requires them to make significant efforts to achieve equal management opportunities with men. To ensure the effectiveness of the organization, it is necessary to take into account the gender factor and comply with gender balance in management positions.

Keywords: gender; management; power; social action; social potential; self-realization

Introduction

The main theoretical and methodological concepts and approaches devoted to gender relations, self-realization of women in the management system, were established in the context of philosophy, history, and sociological science. In their writings, the philosophers Aristotle, Plato, Socrates, and Fomus Aquinat considered women as lower beings in comparison with men. In the Renaissance, as a result of intellectual shift, a positive view of women is formed. In the age of Enlightenment, Jean-Jacques Rousseau admitted equal abilities of men and women, but was a supporter of traditional male power believing that the wife should be humble, obey to her husband and learn to tolerate everything from him, even injustice. Socio-philosophical and political concepts of the XVIII-XX centuries served as intellectual prerequisites for the development of feminism, which played a decisive role in the emergence of a fundamentally new scientific paradigm.

The basis of any social organization is not people in general, but men and women who fulfill their professional and status roles in the organization. Each of them seeks to achieve the desired status, success in the chosen field of activity, to make a career, to receive recognition from others. But gender asymmetry in all spheres of activity is a reflection of these processes.

Purpose

In view of the foregoing, the purpose of the article is to outline the social technologies for improving the management of the organization through the use and implementation of

managerial capacity of men and women, ensuring career growth, confidence in the ability to hold managerial positions on the basis of healthy competition and professional ability.

Statement of basic materials

The natural differences between women and men, perceived in world philosophy and as one of the fundamental foundations of life, as the development of human civilization passes from the scope of pure philosophical reflection in the sphere of socio-philosophical analysis. This shift is very closely related to the very development of the social philosophy of the XXI century, the change of ideas about the nature of the relationship, between the theoretical and methodological layers of social sciences, empirical generalizations and the actual philosophical comprehension of the totality of data in sociology, psychology, anthropology and other sciences. But, in our opinion, the main focus on the problem of "woman-man" affects the change in the position of women in the modern world, which can not be further aware of the positions that are characteristic for the philosophy and social science of past ages.

For centuries, typical ideas concerning the concept of "male" and "feminine" formed and built up, insults and roles inherent in one sex or another. These stereotypes apply to all gender representatives, regardless of individual characteristics, age or origin. They touch not only the personality traits, but also the features of behavior. The exceptional patriarchy of modern society gradually shifts away from the past. The new trend in management leads to the gradual consolidation of women in the field of prominent leaders (Tarkhanova, 2017). Active integration of female and male models of behavior creates preconditions and forms the conscious need to study the gender peculiarities of personality behavior in leadership and organizational and methodological aspects of management, depending on the gender of the head. "Hatred of one gender to another and propensity to low evaluation has always been a sign of the decline and degeneration of the individual, if he/she differs by this property, and even entire peoples, if this phenomenon is becoming widespread" (Bhattacharyya, 2018).

Manipulation that affects representatives of the opposite sex, creating a barrier to career development on a gender basis, choosing a man to head, sexual segregation in interpersonal informal communication are all indicators of unfavorable gender relations in organizations.

It can be said with certainty that the ratio of men and women in managerial positions is changing rapidly and more and more women are involved in managerial activity. It should be noted that while performing the same professional activity, men and women relate to it differently (Skiba, 2015). The former relate to a career as a prestigious position, while others, in part, perceive it as a way of self-actualization.

Women's leadership, as a part of the management system, that develops actively, attracts the attention of many researchers (Pologikh, 2016). There are many opposing views, concepts and research. During the analysis of academic and scientific literature, two main points were identified on gender differences in the management system. One of them is the firm belief in the so-called special, only women decision-making method, the exceptional style of leadership and its value system (Hirst, & Schwabenland, 2018). The other one excludes the difference on the basis of gender typing, which today is not quite accurate (Moskalyk, Baranovska, & Bulach, 2017). It is necessary to understand that they still exist.

Despite the weak distinction between men and women in terms of leadership effectiveness, one should not forget about identifying its situational specifics, where in one role and situation

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a man is more effective, in another – a woman, Peter Schoederbek says, a specialist in management (Schoderbek, Schoderbek, & Kefalas, 1990).

Schoderbek, From this it can be concluded that female executives succeed not as a result of copying the male style of management, but directly using a kind of use of their own abilities, the implementation of internal, only their inherent qualities of personality.

To understand the influence of gender mechanisms on the organization's governance system, it is important to distinguish between the approach of women and men to management and leadership. In this regard, there is a lot of controversy among scientists. Most of them believe that there is no significant difference in how men and women manage an enterprise, an organization (Bhattacharyya, 2018). And the others have the opposite opinion: the male style of leadership is still different from the female and it is more effective (Roberts, 2016). After analyzing the research of various domestic (Korkh, & Khmil, 2014) and foreign scientists (Miller, & Borgida, 2016), one can distinguish the differences that manifested in men and women in management: in the style of leadership, in decision-making, in relation to work and careers. It is important to note that these differences are largely due to the business and personal qualities of representatives of different sexes. For example, E. Dobner writes about the difference in leadership styles. He notes that men often pressure from the top down, thus showing their power, while women are developing solutions together with the team. And German professor G. Heller notes that men in their leadership pursue the goal, women look at people who must achieve this goal (Svergun, 2012, p. 22).

Thus, in professional activity, men and women can exhibit the same qualities, but in different management situations the degree of importance of showing these qualities will be different. Exploring gender differences in management, Yvonne Galligan points out that women choose a relationship-oriented leadership, because they are more emotional by nature and men are more focused on tasks, because they are more often characterized by persistence and perseverance. Also, the male style is more effective either in structured situations and in solving simple tasks, or in situations of high degree of uncertainty, and the female style gives the most efficiency in routine conditions. (Galligan et al., 2017). In part, women are more likely to cope with more responsible tasks than men. From Lisa Hart Shepard's (2018) point of view, male managers often choose an aggressive leadership style, believing that when the leader, according to criteria such as professionalism, experience, competence, resourcefulness, responsibility, willingness to take risks and speed in decision making, prevail over their subordinates, they must comply with his instructions. Andrea Miller and Eugene Borghid (2016) point out that men tend to use contract-style leadership, giving way to working relationships as a series of exchanges – agreements with subordinates in the form of awards for well-executed orders or punish for inappropriate behavior, they often use positional power, seek to increase their authority and improve the methods in leading their subordinates. Their methods are generally aimed at redefining the sphere of rules and norms. Yes, women use their unique ability to communicate and they manage not like men. They achieve success not despite the fact that some human traits have always been considered "female" and unsuitable for a leader, but because of this. Researchers agree only one difference between managers of different sexes: the greater interest of women managers in the relationship between people, which is more a plus in leadership of people. Women's managers not only bring together employees, but also can inspire them, demonstrating enthusiasm even with some minor successes, they are ready for non-standard decisions, to constructive (staffing) reorganizations, to change the methods of management in critical situations (Grishchenko, 2011).

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It is also possible to highlight the differences in making managerial decisions between men and women. Women in leading make decisions on the basis of more cautious strategies, make "balanced" and "cautious" decisions more often, rely on situational management, and male managers tend to a higher degree of risk, make "risky decisions" and prefer dispositional management. This is due to their confidence, the tendency to self-examination and independence in actions, a more pronounced need for self-affirmation. When making important managerial decisions, a woman-manager relies not only on her logic, but also on her intuition and feeling, which often leads to positive results. But at the same time, women tend to be emotional, and this can negatively affect work and making the right decisions. There is a number of differences and, above all, for male and female purposes (plans). If male plans for the future as a whole are of a uniform nature and are related to work, then women's plans are inherently fragmentary, they seek to combine career and marriage. At the same time, women differ in their plans in relation to the traditional role of wife and mother and the prospects of career growth, bending one way or the other, alternating goals or seeking to unite them (Shepherd, 2018). As socio-psychological studies show, women are not less than men interested in moving up the career ladder, but they face with more obstacles on this way. However, in today's society, as already noted above, there are still stereotypes and some contradictions. Therefore, the actual statement is that for women the path to managerial careers is connected with the overcoming of many obstacles, and for men – with the implementation of numerous opportunities.

Various publications devoted to gender issues suggest that from the point of view of leadership effectiveness, there are no fundamental differences between men and women, but they reveal the situational specificity of their manifestations: in some situations and roles, men are more effective, in others – women. Men and women perceive the situation differently and differently position themselves in the workplace. There are differences in perception, in the methods and means used to solve problems in the management style. In general, women tend to believe that the organization is functioning normally if everyone works as a part of the whole. Men, by contrast, believe that everyone is responsible for himself, and the work must be completed on their own. Women also tend to be more supportive and loyal in management, whereas men are more direct and aggressive. Active integration of male and female models of behavior in management creates preconditions and forms the conscious need to study the organizational and methodological aspects of management, depending on the gender characteristics of the behavior of the individual in the construction and implementation of management activities.

It is worth noting that in order to ensure the effectiveness of the organization's activities, it is necessary to consider and study the influence of the gender factor on the effectiveness of management activities. After all, in any team there are situations, problems, questions, when solving will be effective either by men or women. Therefore, for a competent and full-fledged functioning of the organization it is necessary to take into account gender specificity and to respect a gender balance in managerial positions, thus ensuring a competitive advantage. However, despite the fact that most business leaders are aware of this fact, only a handful of people take measures to establish such equilibrium. Among the large-scale Ukrainian organizations, there are still a few of those who have been included women into the leadership (Naumenko, 2017). It is necessary to rethink the current situations in the field of gender management, to develop a new management strategy. Modern organizations need to look closely at the experience of organizations that have managed to create a corporate culture focused on establishing a gender balance, thus they can provide themselves with a serious advantage in the competition.

Originality

Originality of a paper is the further development in the theory of gender processes with application of interdisciplinary approaches in studying the phenomenon of gender, not from the point of view of the interactions between two large social groups (men and women), but as a social resource of an organization where men and women represent labor potential, rational use of which is the key to successful management in the organization. The social potential of Ukrainian women can become a valuable resource in a country, a region, and any social organization.

Conclusions

So, by analyzing the gender aspects of the governance system, one can draw the following conclusion: in a European country and in the USA, a woman has more opportunities, more rights than in Ukraine. According to G. Sillaste, this is due to the fact that capitalism has developed in these countries for 200 years and during this time a woman's question was solved in the context of a market economy. However, in these countries, women's success is due not only to the achievements of the women's movement, but to the fact that human rights are better protected in these countries. Given the gender picture of management activity, innovations are currently needed in order to give women the opportunity to advance in their professional activities, fully implementing their talents and abilities, which will benefit the organization as a whole. In our opinion, a new differentiated approach is needed in order to create a gender balance in the organization. The management ensures public order, which provides success to those who have some aggressiveness, initiative, competitiveness, that is, male traits. To break through in these conditions, women partly have to simulate a model of male behavior. Women face with higher social barriers than men, which explain their backlog in the field of management promotion. The main barriers to women's professional self-realization are, first of all, gender stereotypes, which affect women themselves, as well as due to objective difficulties ("double" employment, unregulated working hours, and stereotypical thinking of male managers). Women who managed to break through the so-called "glass ceiling" continue to fulfill their primary responsibilities related to the upbringing of children, and strive to combine professional activities with the role of mother. We believe that changing traditional socialization and overcoming gender stereotypes at the level of consciousness of men and women, as well as political and organizational measures, in our society should contribute to the establishment of a fair and balanced model of women's participation in management at all levels of government. Self-development, the opportunity to improve their qualifications, gain experience, knowledge, connections, social effects of work, the opportunity to bring real benefits to society are significant indicators of the professional sphere for women.

High evaluation of professional merits of women in the form of decent career growth, trust in them from the leadership will stimulate the professional development of women themselves and increase the efficiency, humanist orientation and democracy of organizations. Women quickly gained experience in managing the organization, focusing on such qualities as high performance, responsibility, self-esteem, flexibility, creativity, intuition, emotional approach to solving managerial problems, the need and ability of constant self-affirmation, so they are able to cope with the tasks of effective management.

Yet a considerable part of purposeful, energetic, ambitious women, willing to work hard and persistently, does not scare that the profession of a manager requires a demanding workload,

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efficiency, perseverance in overcoming a significant number of barriers to achieve self-realization in professional activities.

The essence of the conceptual model in organization management using gender potential is that men and women working in a social organization, regardless of their position, seek professional growth, success and create a positive image around them. We distinguish the social structure of the organization with two axes – vertical and horizontal. Horizontal differentiation includes gender interpersonal relationships, and vertical differentiation is the social status of men and women of the organization. At the intersection of a career and image is success. Such model allows distinguishing four types of gender interactions in the management of an organization: autocratic, obediently dependent, critical, egocentric. The analysis of gender interactions in management has confirmed the low part of women in management, and the higher level of power is completely closed to the rotation of women. In our opinion, the superiority of male-style management in all its pluses still "suffers" from one-sidedness, which ultimately negatively affects management processes.

A social organization should not neglect well-organized skilled labor for both men and women. Since women realize that they work effectively on their workplace, contribute to the organization's activities, feel satisfaction from the possibility in realizing their abilities, strengthening their personal economic independence and from the possibility of improving the financial situation of the family. The reality of the 21st century asserts that a woman is truly successful when she has both professional self-realization and strong family relationships.

In our view, the management system only wins if it involves women, promoting the disclosure of their talents. We note that increasing the social potential of the organization can be due to the full inclusion of women in the management process. Women managers deserve to be appreciated, not to deny their rights, style of behavior that is more adaptive, socially wise, which provides constructive cooperation, mutual understanding and trust. The high managerial potential, possessed by women, can open up new opportunities for Ukraine to social and economic development.

REFERENCES

- Bhattacharyya, R. (2018). What gender is, what gender does. *Gender, Place & Culture*, 25(3), 467-469. doi: 10.1080/0966369X.2017.1338432 (in English)
- Galligan, Y., Hauptfleisch, R., Irvine, L., Korolkova, K., Natter, M., Schultz, U. ... Lazaruk, M. L. (Ed.). (2017). *Mapping the Representation of Women and Men in Legal Professions Across the EU*. Retrieved from [http://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/STUD/2017/596804/IPOL_STU\(2017\)596804_EN.pdf](http://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/STUD/2017/596804/IPOL_STU(2017)596804_EN.pdf) (in English)
- Grishchenko, A. (2011). Pervye zhenshchiny menedzhery. *Upravlenie personalom*, 5, 6-10. (in Russian)
- Hirst, A., & Schwabenland, C. (2018). Doing gender in the "new office". *Gender, Work and Organization*, 25(2), 159-176. doi: 10.1111/gwao.12200 (in English)
- Korkh, O., & Khmil, V. (2014). Transcendental Aspects of Gender. *Anthropological Measurements of Philosophical Research*, 5, 69-76. doi: 10.15802/ampr2014/25045 (in Ukrainian)
- Miller, A., & Borgida, E. (2016). The Separate Spheres Model of Gendered Inequality. *PLoS One*, 11(1), 1-34. doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0147315 (in English)
- Moskalyk, H. F., Baranovska, M. Y., & Bulach, M. O. (2017). Historical-philosophical-legal research of the phenomenon of the gender as the factor of the social status of the Ukrainian woman. *Anthropological Measurements of Philosophical Research*, 12, 100-112. doi: 10.15802/ampr.v0i12.119150 (in Ukrainian)
- Naumenko, R. (2017). Management for the society of the future: New trends in the training for civil servants in Ukraine. *Philosophy and Cosmology*, 19, 117-125. (in English)
- Pologikh, A. (2016). Gender diversity in management and leadership. *Leadership and Management*, 3(2), 73-86. doi: 10.18334/lim.3.2.35170 (in Russian)

SOCIAL ASPECT OF HUMAN BEING

- Roberts, M. (2016). Beyond "Crisis" in understanding gender transformation. *Gender & History*, 28(2), 358-366. doi: 10.1111/1468-0424.12212 (in English)
- Schoderbek, P., Schoderbek, C., & Kefalas, A. (1990). *Management systems: Conceptual considerations*. Homewood, IL: Richard d Irwin. (in English)
- Shepherd, L. (2018). Gender pay gap in the legal sphere? Not in the US. *Lawyer Monthly*. Retrieved from <https://www.lawyer-monthly.com/2018/03/gender-pay-gap-in-the-legal-sphere-not-in-the-us/> (in English)
- Skiba, E. (2015). Power as a source of the constitution of inequality of gender identities. *Grani*, 1(117), 29-33. (in Russian)
- Svergun, O. (2012). Personnel management: A gender perspective. *Spravochnik po upravleniyu personalom*, 6, 69-74. (in Russian)
- Tarkhanova, E. S. (2017). The study of gender differences in the management area. *Science. Society. State*, 5(2). Retrieved from https://esj.pnzgu.ru/files/esj.pnzgu.ru/tarkhanova_es_17_2_23.pdf (in Russian)

LIST OF REFERENCE LINKS

- Bhattacharyya, R. What gender is, what gender does / R. Bhattacharyya // *Gender, Place & Culture*. – 2018. – Vol. 25, Iss. 3. – P. 467–469. doi: 10.1080/0966369X.2017.1338432
- Mapping the Representation of Women and Men in Legal Professions Across the EU [Virtual Resource] / Y. Galligan, R. Hauptfleisch, L. Irvine, K. Korolkova, M. Natter, U. Schultz, S. Wheeler ; Ed. by M. L. Lazaruk. – 2017. – Access Mode: [http://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/STUD/2017/596804/IPOLE_STU\(2017\)596804_EN.pdf](http://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/STUD/2017/596804/IPOLE_STU(2017)596804_EN.pdf) – Title from Screen. – Date of Access: 04.05.2019.
- Грищенко, А. Первые женщины менеджеры / А. Грищенко // *Управление персоналом*. – 2011. – № 5. – С. 6–10.
- Hirst, A. Doing Gender in the "New Office" / A. Hirst, Ch. Schwabenland // *Gender, Work and Organization*. – 2018. – Vol. 25, Iss. 2 – P. 159–176. doi: 10.1111/gwao.12200
- Корх, О. М. Трансцендентні світи гендеру / О. М. Корх, В. В. Хміль // *Антропологічні виміри філософських досліджень*. – 2014. – Вип. 5. – С. 69–76. doi: 10.15802/ampr2014/25045
- Miller, A. The Separate Spheres Model of Gendered Inequality / A. Miller, E. Borgida // *PLoS One*. – 2016. – Vol. 11, Iss. 1. – P. 1–34. doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0147315
- Москалик, Г. Ф. Историко-філософсько-правове дослідження феномену гендера як чинника соціального статусу української жінки / Г. Ф. Москалик, М. Ю. Барановська, М. О. Булах // *Антропологічні виміри філософських досліджень*. – 2017. – Вип. 12. – С. 100–112. doi: 10.15802/ampr.v0i12.119150
- Naumenko, R. Management for the Society of the Future: New Trends in the Training for Civil Servants in Ukraine / R. Naumenko // *Philosophy and Cosmology*. – 2017. – Vol. 19. – P. 117–125.
- Пологих, А. А. Гендерные различия в управлении и лидерстве / А. А. Пологих // *Лидерство и менеджмент*. – 2016. – Т. 3, № 2. – С. 73–86. doi: 10.18334/lim.3.2.35170
- Roberts, M. L. Beyond "Crisis" in Understanding Gender Transformation / M. L. Roberts // *Gender & History*. – 2016. – Vol. 28, Iss. 2. – P. 358–366. doi: 10.1111/1468-0424.12212
- Schoderbek, P. Management Systems : Conceptual Considerations / P. Schoderbek, Ch. G. Schoderbek, A. G. Kefalas. – Homewood, IL : Richard d Irwin, 1990. – 417 p.
- Shepherd, L. Gender Pay Gap in the Legal Sphere? Not in the US [Virtual Resource] / L. Shepherd // *Lawyer Monthly*. – 2018. – 6 Jun. – Access Mode: <https://www.lawyer-monthly.com/2018/03/gender-pay-gap-in-the-legal-sphere-not-in-the-us/> – Title from Screen. – Date of Access: 04.05.2019.
- Скиба, Э. Власть как источник конституирования неравенства гендерных идентичностей / Э. Скиба // *Грани*. – 2015. – № 1 (117). – С. 29–33.
- Свергун, О. Управление персоналом: гендерный подход / О. Свергун // *Справочник по управлению персоналом*. – 2012. – № 6. – С. 69–74.
- Тарханова, Е. С. Исследование гендерных различий в управленческой сфере [Электронный ресурс] / Е. С. Тарханова // *Наука. Общество. Государство*. – 2017. – Т. 5, № 2 (18). – Режим доступа: https://esj.pnzgu.ru/files/esj.pnzgu.ru/tarkhanova_es_17_2_23.pdf (дата обращения 04.05.2019). – Название с экрана.

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ГЕНДЕРНІ АСПЕКТИ ВЗАЄМВІДНОШЕНЬ У СИСТЕМІ УПРАВЛІННЯ

Метою статті є дослідження гендерних аспектів управління та вивчення взаємозв'язку особливостей управлінської діяльності й стилю керівництва від гендерної типізації з метою підвищення ефективності управління. **Теоретичний базис.** Для розуміння впливу гендерних механізмів на систему управління організацією виявляється різниця в підході жінок та чоловіків до управління та керівництва. Наведені основні характеристики чоловічого та жіночого стилю керівництва, особливостей у прийнятті управлінських рішень по відношенню до роботи та кар'єри. **Наукова новизна** роботи полягає в подальшому розвитку теорії гендерних процесів із застосуванням міждисциплінарних підходів при дослідженні феномена гендера не з точки зору взаємодій двох великих соціальних груп (чоловіків та жінок), а як соціального ресурсу організації, де чоловіки та жінки являють собою трудовий потенціал, раціональне використання якого – запорука успішного управління організацією. Соціальний потенціал, яким володіють українські жінки, може стати цінним ресурсом країни, регіону й будь-якої соціальної організації. **Висновки.** У сучасному суспільстві ігнорується унікальний досвід управління жінок, який свідчить про наявність у них значного і маловикористаного управлінського потенціалу. Аналіз гендерних взаємодій в управлінських процесах дозволив виявити активне прагнення жінок до кар'єрного росту, досягнення успіху в індивідуальному іміджі. Однак трансформація гендерної сфери в організації відображає перевагу патріархальних відношень, що слугує перешкодою у просуванні жінок в управлінській структурі і відповідно вимагає від них значних зусиль, направлених на досягнення рівних з чоловіками можливостей у галузі управління. Для забезпечення ефективності діяльності організації необхідно враховувати гендерний фактор і дотримуватися гендерної рівноваги на управлінських посадах.

Ключові слова: гендер; управління; влада; соціальна дія; соціальний потенціал; самореалізація

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ГЕНДЕРНЫЕ АСПЕКТЫ ВЗАИМООТНОШЕНИЙ В СИСТЕМЕ УПРАВЛЕНИЯ

Целью статьи является исследование гендерных аспектов управления и изучения взаимосвязи особенностей управленческой деятельности и стиля руководства от гендерной типизации с целью повышения эффективности управления. **Теоретический базис.** Для понимания влияния гендерных механизмов на систему управления организацией оказывается разница в подходе женщин и мужчин к управлению и руководству. Приведены основные характеристики мужского и женского стиля руководства, особенностей в принятии управленческих решений в отношении работы и карьеры. **Научная новизна** работы заключается в дальнейшем развитии теории гендерных процессов с применением междисциплинарных подходов при исследовании феномена гендера не с точки зрения взаимодействий двух больших социальных групп (мужчин и женщин), а как социальный ресурс организации, где мужчины и женщины представляют собой трудовой потенциал, рациональное использование которого – залог успешного управления организацией. Социальный

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потенциал, которым обладают украинские женщины, может стать ценным ресурсом страны, региона и любой социальной организации. **Выводы.** В современном обществе игнорируется уникальный опыт правления женщин, свидетельствующий о наличии у них значительного и неиспользованного управленческого потенциала. Анализ гендерных взаимодействий в управленческих процессах позволил выявить активное стремление женщин к карьерному росту, достижению успеха. Однако трансформация гендерной сферы в организации отражает предпочтение патриархальных отношений, служит преградой в продвижении женщин в управленческой структуре и соответственно требует от них значительных усилий, направленных на достижение равных с мужчинами возможностей в области управления. Для обеспечения эффективности деятельности организации необходимо учитывать гендерный фактор и соблюдать гендерное равновесие на управленческих должностях.

Ключевые слова: гендер; управление; власть; социальное действие; социальный потенциал; самореализация

Received: 23.09.2018

Accepted: 14.03.2019